

Effect of lactose, yeast and organic acids mixture supplementation on laying performance of Japanese quails (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*)

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Abstract

This study was performed on 180 one week old Japanese quail chicks. They were divided into six groups. Treatments were as follows: G1 (control), G2 (1g lactose/ kg), G3 (3g yeast/ kg), G4 (1g lactose + 3g yeast/ kg), G5 (2g benzoic acid + 5g citric acid / kg) and G6 (1g lactose + 2g benzoic acid +5g citric acid / kg). When the birds reached 42 days of age, all birds were sexed and transferred to layer cages the birds were divided into 6 groups each of 24 birds, which were subdivided into 3 replicates [2 males to 6 females in a 1:3 sex ratio] for 12 weeks reproductive and laying trial. They were fed all dry mash layer diets. The feed additives were continued in the same manner as in growth period. For each replicate, egg number, egg weight and egg mass as well as weekly feed intake, egg production and FCR were recorded. The eggs were collected twice daily from each group, stored at 18°C for 6 days incubated in standard automatic incubator for 17 days to follow the effect of used feed additives on fertility, hatchability and chick quality. At the last three days of each egg collection period, eggs were collected from each replicate to evaluate egg quality traits [shell weight (wt.) and %, shell thickness, shape index, egg yolk wt. and % and albumin wt. and %]. Onset of egg laying and sexual maturity came earlier than the control in all treated groups. Mean egg production recorded higher values in G6, G5 and G2 respectively. Mean FCR was improved numerically in all treated groups when compared with the control. Mean values of egg weight and egg mass were numerically higher in all treated groups than the control. Shell quality parameters were not affected with any treatment compared with the control. While shape index was improved significantly in G2, G4 and G5, with numerical improve in G3 and G6. Mean values of egg albumin and egg yolk weight were improved in all treated groups. Mean values of egg yolk cholesterol were decreased significantly in G5 and G6 while it numerically decreased in other groups compared with the control. Higher fertility was recorded in G2, G5 and G6 respectively. Hatchability% of incubated and fertile eggs was higher than the control especially in G2 and G6. The hatched chick quality was higher than the control in G6, G5 and G2 respectively. Furthermore, all treatments improved hatched chick length when compared to the control.

Keywords: Lactose, Yeast, Organic acids, Laying Japanese quail

Introduction

Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) has distinct characteristics such as rapid growth enabling quail to be marketed for human consumption at 5-6 weeks of age, matures at an early age and is a prolific egg producer. It has also assumed worldwide importance as a laboratory animal (Baumgartner, 1994). Therefore,

commercial quail production has grown steadily in Egypt. There are many nutraceutical components used as alternative strategy after antibiotic prohibition. They include probiotics, prebiotics and organic acids, which have been recognized as having beneficial effects upon nutrient utilization,

growth and health to the same or greater level obtained with antibiotics.

Models describing the effects of yeast on animal production are currently based on the ability of yeast strains to stimulate the growth and activities of gastrointestinal bacteria, but this stimulatory characteristic may not be common to all strains of yeast (Stanley et al., 2004 and Zhang et al., 2005). Many results suggested that, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (SC) could act as a growth promoter; because of its natural improvement of digestibility and absorption of nutrients and controlling infections by enteric pathogens (Onifade et al., 1999; Cruickshank, 2002 and Miazzi et al., 2005). The findings of Zwell (2007); Yalcin et al. (2008) and Yalcin et al. (2009) confirmed that dried baker's yeast supplementation significantly increased egg weight.

In case of poultry species, lactose hypothetically fits within the prebiotic concept, because birds cannot digest it, and it is therefore available to microflora in the hindgut (Denbow, 2000). In addition, lactose is a relatively inexpensive byproduct of the milk industry. Also, the addition of prebiotic and yeast culture to laying quail diets had positive effect on various parameters of laying productivity and quality parameters of eggs (total weights of eggs, bigger number, improved both shell thickness and shape index); where the most important parameter influencing economical results of layer quail farming is average egg production per quail and intensity of lay during the production cycle (Tarasewicz et al. 2004 ;Chen P. and Chen T., 2005; Ramune et al. 2010). Among the candidate replacements for antibiotics are organic acids, both individual acids and blends of several acids. Most gut acidifiers consist of organic acids as acetic acid, propionic acid, citric acid, butyric acid, fumaric acid and benzoic acid. Combining the acids may increase the range of desirable antimicrobial

effects (Dhawale, 2005). Supplementation of citric acid in the diet had positive effects on growth, feed intake, feed efficiency, carcass yield, bone ash, and immune status of broilers (Chowdhury et al., 2009). Citric acid may change the intestinal pH for better phytase activity. Physical effect of citric acid on the chemical bonds between phytic acid with fiber, amino acids and protein can be helpful to make them more accessible to endogenous enzymes (Atapattu and Nelligaswatta, 2005). Benzoic acid is extensively used as food preservative in human nutrition. Preliminary results from an experiment with broiler chickens do indicate that it may have a positive influence on growth (Dhawale, 2005). The addition of organic acids into layer diets has a beneficial influence improved egg production (Gama et al. 2000); Bahnas 2009 and Soltan 2008). Reports on effect of lactose as a prebiotic and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, citric and benzoic acids mixture or data of their combinations on laying Japanese quails are limited. The present study aimed to investigate the effect of incorporating lactose, yeast and organic acids mixture (OAM) in diets of laying Japanese quails on their effect on laying and reproductive performance parameters.

Materials and Methods

Diet and management

A total of a 180 unsexed Japanese quails, one-week- old were purchased from Agricultural Technological Center, Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt. Chicks were randomly divided into six groups of average body weight (30.5g). Each treatment group contained 30 birds which were subdivided into three replicates, each of 10 chicks. G1 the first treatment group was the control group was fed the growth basal diet without any supplements added. The second treatment group G2 was fed the basal diet with supplementation of

1g lactose/ kg (Lactose monohydrate A.R C12H22O11.H2O, WINLAB. M.W 360.31, UK). The third treatment group G3 was fed the basal diet with supplementation of 3g yeast/ kg (Instant dried yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, PANTHER, 8×10^9 c.f.u. Turkey). The fourth treatment group G4 was fed the basal diet with supplementation of 1g lactose + 3g yeast/ kg. The fifth treatment group G5 was fed the basal diet with supplementation of 5g citric acid+ 2g benzoic acid / kg (Citric Acid Monohydrate, C6H8.H2O, SIGMA. FW 210.1, Austria. Benzoic Acid A.R C7H6O2, WINLAB. M.W 122.12, Assay 99.5%, UK). The sixth treatment group G6 was fed the basal diet with supplementation of 1g lactose + 5g citric acid+ 2g benzoic acid / kg. According to Hassan et al. (2003) chicks were housed in wire battery cages of 86 L×50 W×25 H cm which were equally partitioned. The chicks were allowed *ad libitum* access to feed and water. Ventilation and temperature (31°C-22°C) were controlled to maintain bird comfort during the grow-out. Birds were provided 24 hours of lighting and checked three times daily (at 6 am, 2 pm and 10 pm) for food, water and mortality. Diet for growth period was formulated to meet the nutritional requirements as suggested by the NRC (1994), as shown in Table (1) corn-soybean meal basal diet was formulated to contain 24% CP and 2900 kcal ME/kg. When the birds reached 42 days old, all birds were sexed and transferred to layer cages of 86 L×50 W×35 H cm. The birds were divided into 6 groups each of 24 birds, which were subdivided into 3 replicates, 2 males to 6 females in a 1:3 sex ratio (Woodard et al., 1973) for 12 weeks reproductive and laying trial. They were fed all dry mash layer basal diets containing the nutritional requirements according to NRC (1994) and containing 20% CP and 2900 Kcal ME/kg diet (Table 1). Each group received the same feed additive that was

taken during the growth period. Data collection was started when birds reached a 65% egg production rate after a two-week pretest period (the 7th and 8th weeks). Body weight (g) was recorded at the beginning of each experimental period. Three consecutive egg collection periods began from (8-12), (12-16) and (16-20) weeks of age. According to Yalcin et al. (2008), an artificial lighting program 17 hr. light (L): 7 hr. dark (D) was followed through the experimental periods.

Reproductive performance

At the first week of the experimental period, the eggs were collected twice daily from each group, stored at 18°C for 6 days according to Petek et al. (2005), eggs incubated in standard automatic incubator for 17 days (14 day incubation at 37.5°C with 65% relative humidity (RH) and 3 days at hatcher with 75% RH), to follow the effect of used feed additives on fertility, hatchability and chick quality as follows: at hatching, the sound chicks, the dead in shells, pipped eggs that do not hatch and abnormal chicks were recorded. Also clear infertile eggs were recorded according to Hassan et al. (2003).

Fertility% = (No. of fertile eggs/ No. of setting eggs) x 100.

Hatchability% of incubated eggs = (No. of released chicks/ total No. of egg placed into incubator) x 100.

Hatchability% of fertile eggs = (No. of released chicks/ No. of fertilized eggs placed into incubator) x 100.

Chick quality

Average weight of a day old chick was recorded and used as an indicator for chick quality. The new standard for measuring chick quality as reported by Luiten (2003), the more practical way to measure chick development is measuring the length of the stretched hatched chicks. The length of the stretched hatched chicks, measured from tip

of the beak to the middle toe (cm) was recorded for all hatched chicks.

Laying performance

For each replicate, egg No. and egg weight (using electric balance with sensitivity of 0.0001) were recorded daily and feed intake was calculated weekly. Egg mass was calculated by multiplying egg No. by average egg weight (Olawumi and Ogunlade, 2008). Feed conversion (g feed/ g egg) was calculated after subtracting the male consumption from the total amount of the feed consumed and protein conversion ratio: PCR = g protein/ g egg.

Egg quality traits

At the last three days of each egg collection period, eggs were collected from each replicate to evaluate egg quality traits. These collected eggs were numerated and weighed; then the width and length of the eggs were measured by caliper. Thereafter, the eggs were broken; the yolk separated from the albumen and the yolk weight was obtained. The shells were washed under slightly flowing water so that the albumen remains are removed. The washed shells were left to dry in the open air for 24 hours. Then, they were weighed together with the shell membrane. Finally egg shell samples taken from sharp end, blunt end and equatorial parts were measured, and the average shell thickness was obtained from the average values of these three parts (Tyler, 1961). Some internal and external quality traits of the egg were estimated using following formulae on the basis of the aforementioned measures:

Egg surface area (S) (cm²) = 3.9782 W^{0.75056} W = Egg weight (mg) (Olawumi and Ogunlade, 2008).

Shape index (%) = [Width (cm) / Height (cm)] x 100

Shell ratio (%) = (Shell weight / Egg Weight) x 100

Albumen weight (g) = Egg weight (EW) - (Yolk weight + Shell weight)

EW= Egg weight (g) (Altan et al., 1995 and Yalcin et al., 1990).

Determination of cholesterol level of quail egg yolk

According to Pasin et al. (1998), rapid determination of total cholesterol in egg yolk using commercial diagnostic cholesterol kits was carried out. For this determination 0.01ml of the cholesterol sample, either standard or egg yolk was mixed with 0.1 ml of 2% NaCl soln. (w/v) and 1 ml enzyme reagent (cholesterol esterase, cholesterol oxidase and peroxidase). A blank was prepared by substituting 0.01ml of deionized water for cholesterol sample. The final volume of each reaction mixture was 1.11ml. Samples were vortexed, and then incubated for 15 min in a water bath at 37°C. Absorbance were read at 500nm using a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-160; Shimadzu Scientific Instruments, Columbia, MD).

Statistical analysis

Duncan multiple ranges Duncan (1955) was used to compare mean among groups according to Snedecore and Cochran (1989). The estimation was made using SPSS 16 (Coakes et al., 2009).

Results and Discussion

Dietary feed additives had no significant effect on average of body weight during the entire period of experiment (Table, 2). This is in agreement with, Önoğlu and Yalçın (1995) and Yalçın et al. (2009) who observed that mean body weight values of laying hens were not affected by the addition of baker's yeast. In contrast to present results Tarasewicz (1998) and Tarasewicz et al. (1998) and also in the research by Ammerman (1989), Waldroup et al. (1993) and Tarasewicz et al. (2004) who observed a positive effect of dietary prebiotic oligosaccharides on weight gain during periods of egg production. The onset

of egg laying was different among groups due to dietary feed additives where, the earliest one was in G4, G5 at 38 days of age then G2, G3 and G6 at 39 days of age, in comparison to the control which was at 42 day of age (Table 2) that may resulted in more economic profitability. Kirchgessner and Roth (1988) stated that, dietary acidification increased gastric proteolysis and protein and amino acid digestibility. Organic acids serve as substrates in intermediary metabolism. The improvement in body weight gain of birds fed citric acid may be due to the utilization of minerals that positively affecting the growth Abd El-Hakim et al. (2009) that may reflect on time of maturity and productivity. The flock's productivity was about 50% after an average of eight days from the egg laying onset, Table (2). According to Shanawany (1994) the period of full maturation, that is when the flock achieves 50% of egg laying capacity, depends on the day length. Sakurai (1983) who kept the quail flock in the regime 16L: 8D, reported that the 50% egg production was reached at 55 days of age, whereas in a short daylight regime (8L: 16D) at 70 days of age while the present study used regime 17L: 7D with different dietary feed additives. Tarasewicz (1998) investigated the effect of oligosaccharides on Pharaohs quail laying performance and observed that, studied quails began and completed their maturation a little earlier. All feed additives used in the present study significantly achieved earlier 50% egg laying capacity when compared to the control one; and this in harmony with Tarasewicz et al. (2004). Mean egg production % recorded higher values in G6 followed by G5 and G2 (Table 2). Boling et al. (2001) investigated the effect of OA addition according to the available phosphorous (AP) level and observed that, lowering the AP level (less than 0.2%) and feeding OA decreased productivity, hen-day

egg production, and the FCR. But supplementation of OA when the AP level was at higher than 0.2% improved productivity and FCR, similar to the results of the present experiment. Radu-Rusu and Pop (2009) cited that, Major influence on the laying hens' health and production is given by the relationship existing between intestinal bacterial population, gut morphology, immune system and nutrients absorption. Some previous researches proved that the commercial mannanoligosaccharide containing product, which issued from the cell wall of the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* yeast, could generate beneficial effects, such as combat against intestinal pathogen germs in birds and mammals, through the immune response modulation and through the improvement of the intestinal mucosal structural integrity (Spring et al., 2000). Prebiotics also improve the absorption of the nutrients, including macro and microelements, through the intestinal wall Pop (2002) and Chen and Chen (2004), increasing meantime the degree of their availability to be used for organism's maintenance and regeneration, as good as for production. Tarasewicz et al. (2004) observed the highest egg laying capacity calculated for 12-week laying period was elevated in group fed elevated level of oligosaccharide to 3g/kg feed when compared to the control. In the deep litter trial, MOS supplementation had no influence on egg production except during the third period (Shashidhara and Devegowda, 2003). On the contrary, Guerrero (1995), Berry and Lui (2000), and Stanley et al. (2000) have reported considerable improvement in egg production in the MOS-fed birds. The MOS reduces the pathogenic bacteria load in the intestine and prevents the acute immune response against such bacteria (Finucane et al., 1999 and Spring et al., 2000). Accordingly, it was hypothesized that nutrients are efficiently

diverted toward production in MOS-fed birds, which might improve egg production in layers and breeders. One reason of numerical not statistical increase of production, may be due to the lower level of lactose inclusion might not have been enough to significantly influence egg production. Additional research will be required to determine whether a higher level of lactose inclusion is required to improve egg production in quail breeder hens. The overall egg production percentages were numerically highest in G6 among all groups. Organic acid combination with lactose G6 increased percentage of egg production by about 4.7% while G2 and G5 by 1.1% and 1.9% respectively, but other dietary treatments did not affect the production percent. That in harmony with Bahnas (2009) who concluded that, malic acid (MA) supplementation caused a significant improvement in egg production capacity %. Final better results in G6 are in accordance with Gama et al. (2000) and Yesilbag and Colpan (2006) and Swiatkiewicz et al. (2010) who studied the effect of organic acids mixtures (formic and propionic) on laying performance of Lohman layers and they observed an improved laying rate as a result of the inclusion of 0.5-1.5% organic acid mixture (OAM) in the diet. Concerning to final results due to addition of yeast and yeast plus lactose are in harmony with Ali (2007) who observed that, increasing yeast culture (YC) to 3 kg/ton diet had no effect on egg production%. Cumulative feed intake over the three periods of experiment showed non-significant increase (Table 2) due to dietary OAM, OAM with lactose and lactose respectively, while yeast and yeast plus lactose did not show any effect on feed intake. Results of yeast and yeast plus lactose are in contrary to Ali (2007) who observed that, increasing YC to 3 kg/ton diet improved EE, CF, and NFE digestibility however; feed intake was significantly

improved when laying hens fed diets low in protein level and supplemented with YC where, the present study used isonitrogenous diets for all treated groups. Also Zeinab et al. (2001) observed that, addition of yeast containing probiotic significantly reduced feed intake and improved feed conversion when compared to the control. Similar to the present study some researchers Bornstein et al. (1982), Rojas Ramirez et al. (1985) and Önoel and Yalçın (1995) observed that, diets containing different species of yeasts had no effect on the feed intake of laying hens. Table (2) demonstrates the effect of different dietary treatments on FCR and PCR of laying J. quail. It was observed a non-significant improvement in FCR in feed additive groups (g feed/g egg). The control group recorded the highest FCR value and protein conversion ratio (g protein/g egg) that reflect enhanced protein utilization in treated groups. Feed conversion ratio due to dietary OAM and OAM with lactose somewhat improved and agreed with Park et al. (2009) who observed that, 0.2% OA resulted in improvement of FCR in laying hens. Egg quality and productivity are the most important parameters for both producers and researchers (Yuan et al., 1994). Egg quantity and quality are dependent on assimilation of nutrients in the organism of layers, because major amount of energy from feed is used for production of eggs (Robinson et al., 1998). Egg weight and egg mass were numerically improved in feed additive groups compared to the control, with highest value in G6 followed by G5 (Table 3). Increased egg weight due to 0.3 % *S.C.* agreed with Yalcin et al. (2008), Liu et al. (2002) and Abou El-Ella et al. (1996) who observed that, egg weight and mass were significantly increased by 2 g/kg commercial yeast culture product *S.C.* supplementation to the laying hen diets. Contrary to Ali (2007) who concluded that, yeast culture had no effect on egg

production, egg weight, and egg mass when laying quail hens fed diets supplemented with 0.3% YC. Also contrary to results of Onol and Yalcin (1995) and Yalcin et al. (2009) as they indicated that, diets containing 5, 10 and 20% of baker's yeast had no effect on egg weight of laying hens. Other researchers Shyam Sunder et al. (1990) and Gar et al. (2001) also observed that, egg weight was not affected by the usage of a different species of yeasts in laying hen diets. Findings of the present study consisted with Chen and Chen (2005) who observed an increased weekly cumulative egg weight per bird after three weeks of feeding prebiotic supplemented diets. Also it was observed after a 4-week feeding trial, that layers fed prebiotic, produced more eggs than the control (by 2.63% at 27 weeks and by 13.35% at 57 weeks). Egg shell quality is an important parameter for producers as it is easier to handle and transport eggs with thicker shell. For having thick egg shell it is important to ensure good absorption of calcium and some other minerals from the feed in the GI tract of quails. Table (3) showed results of egg shell quality and revealed that, shell quality parameters were not affected by feed additive treatments compared with the control. This is in accordance with researchers who indicated that 5, 10 and 20% of baker's yeast Onol and Yalcin (1995) and 10% inactive dry yeast Shyam Sunder et al. (1990) had no significant effect on egg shell thickness. There is some evidence that feed additives increasing the availability of Ca and other minerals may improve hen eggshell quality. The results of some studies carried out on rats, broiler chickens and pigs have indicated that organic acids may improve the utilization of minerals in monogastric animals (Lutz and Scharrer, 1991; Radcliffe et al., 1998; Boling et al., 2000; Mroz et al., 2000; Omogbenigun et al., 2003 and Liem et al.,

2008). One of the mechanisms of this effect is connected with the reduction of intestinal pH, which leads to an increase in the activity of digestive enzymes (accelerated conversion of pepsinogen to pepsin) and in the solubility of minerals. Some experiments with layers and old broiler breeder hens have demonstrated that organic acids can have a positive effect on laying performance and eggshell quality (Park et al., 2002; Yesilbag and Colpan, 2006; Sengor et al., 2007 and Soltan, 2008). In a recent study with older laying hens (from 75 to 80 weeks of age) organic acids beneficially affected soft-shell + broken egg production, feed conversion ratio and IgY concentration in yolks, but had no influence on laying rate and eggshell strength and thickness (Park et al., 2009). The significant decrease in egg shell percentages in all dietary treatments than the control (Table, 3) may be due to increased weight of egg yolk and albumin (Table, 3) on expense of shell weight. In the present study, a positive effect of the prebiotic lactose on some egg shell quality parameters (eggshell weight) in hens (Table, 3). Experimental data on the effect of the prebiotics on eggshell quality are scarce. The results obtained by Yildiz et al. (2006) were somewhat similar to findings of the present study; they observed no statistically confirmed effect of inulin from dried Jerusalem artichoke on the weight, thickness and breaking strength of eggshells during a 16-week trial with layers. Moreover, findings of the study were somewhat contrary to Chen and Chen (2004) who reported that, supplementation of 1% oligofructose or inulin to the diet significantly increased eggshell percent and eggshell breaking strength. Also Yesilbag and Colpan (2006) observed no effect of formic and propionic acids on eggshell thickness and eggshell breaking strength. It has also been proposed that organic acids (citric acid) improved Ca availability by

chelating Ca and reducing the formation of insoluble Ca-phytate complexes (Boling et al., 2000). Abdel-Fattah et al. (2008) reported that, chicks fed a diet supplemented with organic acids had significantly higher blood Ca and P concentrations, which the authors attributed to the lowering of intestinal pH and the increase in the absorption of these macroelements by the utilization of these acids. Egg shape index also is one of the important parameters (Table, 3) eggs with higher index have more round shape, better yolk and white ratio, more dry substance and therefore have higher nutritional value Cepulienė et al. (2010). Overall means of egg shape index in the trial groups (Table, 3) was significantly higher due to supplementation with lactose, yeast plus lactose and OAM, where yeast and OAM with lactose were numerically higher than the control. A significant response due to dietary feed additives was reflected on egg surface area (Table, 3) compared to the control. That parameter may indicate increased egg size and confirm the improved shape index due to the used additives. Weights and percentages concerning egg white and yolk represented in Table (3). It showed that, a significant response due to the used dietary feed additives on egg albumin and yolk weights. Typically this effect was reported by Cepulienė et al. (2010) they used the yeast culture in laying quail hens' diets that may be due to better yolk and white ratio. Contrary to Abou El-Ella et al. (1996) who observed that, egg shape index was not affected by yeast culture supplementation. Also Yalcin et al. (2008) reported that, feeding local laying hens supplemental yeast culture, had no effect on egg shape index, shell weight percentage, albumen index, albumen weight percentage, yolk index, yolk weight percentage, and haugh units. Eggs are an excellent source of amino acids, fatty acids, vitamins, and minerals. Since

1972, poultry scientists have been seeking ways to decrease egg cholesterol concentrations, because of recommendations to limit egg consumption by the public to no more than 3 eggs per week, not to exceed cholesterol intake of 300 mg/d (McNamara, 2000). Egg yolk is also one of the most important sources of cholesterol and, as such, one of the highly risky factors in human nutrition. The level of yolk cholesterol in hen eggs may be decreased by targeted nutrition of hens and selection of genetically suitable breeds (Baumgartner et al., 2001). Although there is no clear evidence relating egg consumption and cardiovascular diseases, recommendations on dietary cholesterol and egg intake led to the cholesterol phobia all over the world. As a result, egg consumption has declined in most developed countries (Zeidler, 2000). Table (3) showed a significant decrease of yolk cholesterol due to supplementation of OAM and OAM with lactose, also other dietary feed additives had numerically lowering effect on yolk cholesterol compared to the control. Present results coincided with Mohan et al. (1995) who reported that, mean egg yolk cholesterol values in laying hens were decreased by the supplementation of probiotic containing *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Aspergillus oryzae*, and *Torulopsis*. Also by yeast cultures only (Yalcin et al., 2008). Also Panda et al. (2003) reported that, probiotics reduced the level of serum and egg yolk cholesterol and increased egg yield, weight and thickness of eggshell and blood calcium. This reduction in egg yolk cholesterol might be explained by the reduced absorption, synthesis, or both, of cholesterol in the gastrointestinal tract. Moreover, Grunewald (1982) reported that, decreasing of cholesterol may be the result of breaking down of cholesterol to bile acids which prevent the renovation of cholesterol. The

addition of acidifiers (phosphoric acid and citric acid) to the diet for broilers lowered the pH of the crop and gizzard content (Park et al., 2009). Bahnas (2009) observed that malic acid supplementation caused significant decrease in yolk cholesterol % in high and low protein –diets.

There were a trend of increase in fertility% in groups fed lactose (G2), OAM (G5) and OAM with lactose (G6) (Table, 4) while other supplementations had no effect. Hatchability % of incubated and fertile eggs was higher than the control especially in G2 and G6. The results were in accordance with Guclu (2011) who investigated the effects of probiotic and prebiotic (mannan-oligosaccharide, MOS) supplementation on performance, egg quality and hatchability in quail breeders and observed that, supplementation of 0.5 to 1 kg/ ton prebiotic slightly but not significantly increased percentage of fertile egg and hatchability. Several workers have reported higher antioxidant activity in chickens and piglets fed MOS-supplemented diets (Zhou et al., 1999 and Shao et al., 2000). From this

perspective, a key aspect that should be deliberated upon is possible improvement in the activity of antioxidants such as glutathione peroxidase (GSHPx) and superoxide dismutase (SOD) in MOS-fed birds and its importance in spermatozoa production and maturation. High levels of GSH-Px are observed in the testes, and it acts as a powerful antioxidant in the developing spermatids and spermatozoa (Ursini et al., 1999). Spermatozoa are subject to the damaging effects of high concentrations of peroxides in testes, semen, and uterovaginal sperm host glands (Lenzi et al., 2000 and Surai et al., 2001). Shashidhara and Devegowda (2003) studied the effects of mannan oligosaccharide (MOS) supplementation in broiler breeder diets on egg production, hatchability, fertility, and immunity and observed that, hatchability of fertile eggs set and fertility were higher ($P \leq 0.05$) in the MOS fed group. He attributed the data on higher hatchability of total eggs set (TES) and hatchability on fertile eggs set (FES) that, higher sperm density in MOS-fed males.

Table (1): Composition and calculated chemical analysis of the experimental basal diets

Ingredients	Growth basal diet %	Layer basal diet
Ground yellow corn	57.83	63.92
Soya bean meal (45%)*	32.94	19.66
Fish meal (60.5%)*	3.50	2.90
Corn gluten (62%)*	3.48	6.40
Dicalcium Phosphate	0.33	0.83
Limestone	1.16	5.52
DL – Methionine	0.09	0.07
Lysine	0.07	0.10
Iodized sodium chloride	0.30	0.30
Mineral& Vitamins premix*	0.30	0.30
Calculated composition		
Crude protein (%)	24.00	20.00
ME (kcal per kg)	2900.00	2900.0
Calorie/protein ratio(C/P)	120.83	145.00
Calcium (%)	0.80	2.50
Available phosphorus (%)	0.30	0.35

* Determined values. ** Each 3 kg contain the following vitamins and minerals: Vit. A 12 mIU, vit. D₃ 2 mIU, vit. E 1000mg, vit. k₃ 1000mg, vit. B₁ 1000mg, vit. B₂ 5000mg, vit. B₆ 1500mg, vit. B₁₂ 10mg, biotin 50mg, pantothenic acid 10g, nicotinic acid 30g, folic acid 1000mg, manganese 60g, zinc 50g, iron 30g, copper 4g, iodine 300mg, selenium 100mg, cobalt 100mg, carrier(CaCO₃) to 3kg. (Goldenpremix - Selim Pharm Elasher, Egypt).

Table (2): Laying performance of experimental groups.

Parameters	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6
Body weight	320.6±4.6	315.9±8.9	327.1±0.4	320.9±1.9	317.8±10.9	318.8±17.1
Laying onset (age in day)	42.3±0.3	39.0±0	39.0±0	38.0±0	38.0±0	39.0±0
50% egg laying (age in day)	51.0±0.5c	47.3±0.3ab	47.3±0.8ab	49.0±0.5b	46.6±0.3a	47.6±0.3ab
Mean egg production%	79.4±4.6	80.3±2.7	79.6±7.9	76.9±9.3	80.9±5.5	83.1±5.1
Daily feed intake	26.9±0.5	27.6±1.1	26.9±0.1	27.1±0.8	28.3±0.7	28.9±0.8
Average egg weight	12.66±0.3	13.76±0.55	13.4±0.4	12.9±0.3	13.8±0.5	14.1±0.5
FCR (feed g/ egg g)	2.13±0.01	2.02±0.08	2.01±0.05	2.1±0.06	2.06±0.07	2.07±0.07
PCR	2.36±0.06 ^{ab}	2.36±0.03 ^{ab}	2.53±0.03 ^a	2.26±0.06 ^b	2.30±0 ^{ab}	2.30±0.15 ^{ab}

Values are means ± standard error (SE). Means within the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($P<0.05$). G1= control; G2=0.1% lactose; G3=0.3% yeast; G4=0.1% lactose +0.3% yeast; G5=0.5% citric acid+0.2% benzoic acid; G6=0.5% citric acid+0.2% benzoic acid +0.1% lactose.

Table (3): Egg quality traits in experimental groups.

Parameters	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6
Mean egg weight	12.66±0.3	13.76±0.55	13.40±0.4	12.90±0.3	13.80±0.5	14.10±0.5
Total egg mass/hen g	283.3±21.6	314.5±25.5	302.4±39.2	283.8±40.5	301.4±24.5	333.8±34.9
Egg shell weight g	1.13±0.02	1.2±0.03	1.13±0.04	1.15±0.04	1.17±0.04	1.22±0.02
Egg shell %	8.7±0.2 ^a	7.9±0.1 ^b	7.9±0.2 ^b	7.9±0.1 ^b	7.5±0.2 ^{bc}	7.2±0.1 ^c
Shell thickness mm	0.25±0.01	0.24±0.01	0.25±0.01	0.26±0.01	0.24±0.01	0.25±0.01
Mean shape index	76.3±0.5 ^b	80.4±0.5 ^a	78.4±1.4 ^{ab}	79.8±0.6 ^a	79.5±0.3 ^a	78.5±1.1 ^{ab}
Egg surface area cm ²	4.8±0.1 ^d	5.5±0 ^b	5.2±0.1 ^c	5.3±0.1 ^{bc}	5.5±0.1 ^b	5.9±0.1 ^a
Egg albumin weight g	7.4±0.2 ^c	8.7±0.2 ^{ab}	8.2±0.7 ^{ab}	8.3±0.1 ^{bc}	9.3±0.1 ^{ab}	9.8±0.1 ^a
Egg albumin %	57.8±0.7	57.6±0.5	61.7± 5.6	56.8±0.2	59.6±0.6	58.2±0.9
Yolk cholesterol mg/100g	1836.5±13 ^a	1802.9±22 ^a	1754.7±33 ^a	1832.2±7 ^a	1595.3±20 ^b	1549.3±85 ^b
Egg yolk weight g	4.3±0.02 ^c	5.2±0.1 ^b	5.2±0.1 ^b	5.1±0.1 ^b	5.1±0.06 ^b	5.9±0.3 ^a
Egg yolk%	33.4±0.5 ^b	34.4±0.6 ^{ab}	36.6±1.3 ^a	35.2±0.2 ^{ab}	32.8±0.8 ^b	34.6±1.1 ^{ab}

Values are means ± standard error (SE). Means within the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($P<0.05$). G1= control; G2=0.1% lactose; G3=0.3% yeast; G4=0.1% lactose +0.3% yeast; G5=0.5% citric acid+0.2% benzoic acid; G6=0.5% citric acid+0.2% benzoic acid +0.1% lactose.

Table (4): Reproductive performance and chick quality in experimental groups.

Parameters	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6
Fertility % of incubated eggs	87.5±2.3	90.9±1.7	87.8±2.1	84.8±1.5	90.6±0.3	89.8±1.9
Hatchability % of incubated eggs	70.6±2.9 ^b	79.5±1.7 ^a	73.7±2.9 ^{ab}	71.1±2 ^b	74.7±3.1 ^{ab}	77.1±1.7 ^{ab}
Hatchability % of fertile eggs	80.6±1.2	87.4±2.7	84.1±4.2	83.8±2.4	82.5±3.6	85.7±1.7
Mean chick weight g	9.0±0.1 ^{bc}	9.2±0.1 ^b	9.1±0.1 ^b	8.7±0.1 ^c	9.2±0.1 ^b	9.9±0.1 ^a
Mean chick length cm	10.5±0.2 ^c	11.6±0.1 ^a	11.6±0.1 ^a	11.0±0.1 ^b	11.6±0.1 ^a	12.0±0.1 ^a

Values are means ± standard error (SE). Means within the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($P<0.05$). G1= control; G2=0.1% lactose; G3=0.3% yeast; G4=0.1% lactose +0.3% yeast; G5=0.5% citric acid+0.2% benzoic acid; G6=0.5% citric acid+0.2% benzoic acid +0.1% lactose.

However, Roque and Soares (1994) suggested that the increase in hatchability may be due to the increased egg shell thickness. Also Eslick and McDaniel (1992) observed progressive improvement in hatchability on TES and FES as the number of sperm deposited increased.

There are several factors that affect the hatchability. It is presumed that, influences

of environmental factors on the difference in hatchability among treatments are negligible because hatching eggs from treated groups were subjected to the same environmental variation during storage and incubation. Differences in hatchability (TES and FES) in the trial may be due to higher sperm density in MOS-fed males Shashidhara and Devegowda (2003), as observed in the G2.

Reports concerning to lactose supplementation and its effect on hatchability in quail hen breeders are limited.

Improvements in hatchability have been observed in birds fed a yeast culture supplement in the present study, these results are in agreement with the findings of McDaniel (1991), McDaniel and Sefton (1991) and Sefton (1991) who concluded that, higher fertility in the MOS group; sperm number in the oviduct seemed to be the crucial factor responsible for differences in fertility among the treatments. Also addition of lactose resulted in a significant increase in harvested chicks from incubated eggs (Table, 4) when compared with the control with the numerical improvement in other additive treated ones. Also, Hatchability % of fertile eggs was numerically increased when compared to the control. These results agreed with Tarasewicz et al. (2004) who observed that, oligosaccharide prebiotics improved the hatchability indices of set and fertilized eggs of laying Japanese quails. Dietary feed additives G6, G5, G2, and G3 significantly improved weight of hatched chicks compared with the control (Table, 4). Measuring length of newly hatched chick is the more practical way to evaluate chick development due to dietary feed additive Luiten (2003), (Table, 4) showed significant improvement of hatched chick's length due to dietary additives compared with the control.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that, supplementation of 0.3% yeast, 0.1% lactose and OAM or OAM with lactose to the diet of egg laying J. quail improved egg production and egg quality, reduced egg yolk cholesterol and positively affected fertility, hatchability and hatched chick quality. One tenth % lactose, OAM and OAM with lactose have the highest

positive effect on egg production, fertility and chick quality.

References

- Abd El-Hakim, A. S.; Cherian, G. and Ali, M. N. (2009): Use of organic acid, herbs and their combination to improve the utilization of commercial low protein broiler diets. *Inter. J. Poult. Sci.* 8 (1): 14-20.
- Abdel-Fattah, S. A.; EI-Sanhoury, M. H.; EI-Mednay, N. M. and Abdul-Azeem, F. (2008): Thyroid activity of broiler chicks fed supplemental organic acids. *Int. J. Poult. Sci.* 7:215–222.
- Abou El-Ella, M. A.; Attia, M. Y.; El-Nagmy, K. Y. and Radwan, M. A. H. (1996): The productive performance of layers fed diets supplemented with some commercial feed additives. *Egypt. J. Anim. Prod. Suppl.* 33: 423–430.
- Ali, A. M. (2007): Nutritional interrelationships between dietary protein level and yeast culture supplementation for laying Japanese quail. *4th the worlds poultry conference*; March 27-28-2008 (429-447).
- Altan, O., I. Oguz and Settar, P. (1995): Japon bildircinlarinda yumurta agirligi ile ozgul agirliginin kulucka ozelliklerine etkileri. *Turk. J. Agri. Forestry*, 19: 219-222.
- Ammerman, E.; Quarles, C. and Twining, P. V. Jr (1989): Evaluation of fructooligosaccharides on performance and carcass yield of male broilers. *Poult. Sci.*, 68 (Suppl.): 167.
- Atapattu, N. S. B. M. and Nelligaswatta, C. J. (2005): Effects of citric acid on the performance and the utilization of phosphorous and crude protein in broiler chickens fed on rice by-products based diets. *Int. J. Poult. Sci.* 4, 990–993.
- Bahnas, M. S. (2009): Effect of using malic acid on performance of Japanese quail fed optimal and sub-optimal energy and protein levels. *Egypt. Poult. Sci. Vol. (29) (I)*: 263-286.

- Baumgartner, J. (1994): Japanese quail production, breeding and genetics. *Worl. Poult. Sci. J.*, 50: 227-235.
- Baumgartner, J.; Benkova, J.; Šarnikova, B. and Polacikova, M. (2001): The performance index on the quality of eggs of laying hens crossbred with the lower yolk cholesterol. *J. F. Anim. Sci.*, 34, 275–282.
- Berry, W. D. and Lui, P. (2000): Egg production, egg shell quality and bone parameters in broiler breeder hens receiving Bio- Mos and Eggshell 49. *Poult. Sci.* 79 (Suppl. 1):124. (Abstr.).
- Boling, S. D.; Douglas, M. W.; Snow, J. L.; Parsons, C. and Baker, D. H. (2000): Citric acid does not improve phosphorus utilization in laying hens fed a corn-soybean meal diet. *Poult. Sci.*, 79, 1335-1337.
- Boling, S. D.; Snow, J. L.; Parsons, C. M. and Baker, D. H. (2001): The effect of citric acid on calcium and phosphorus requirements of chicks fed corn soybean meal diets. *Poult. Sci.*, 80: 783-788.
- Bornstein, S.; Plavnik, I. and Lipstein B. (1982): Evaluation of methanol-grown bacteria and hydrocarbon-grown yeast as sources of protein for poultry: trials with laying birds. *Br. Poult. Sci.* 23, 487–499.
- Čepulienė, R.; Gudavičiūtė, D.; Semaška, V.; Bobinienė, R.; Kepalienė, I.; Vencius, D. and Sirvydis, V. (2010): Effect of the yeast culture feed additive on productivity and egg quality of laying quails. *Veterinarian IR Zootechnika (Vet Med Zoot)*. T. 52 (74).
- Chen, P. and Chen, T. (2005): Improved Layer Performance and Reduced Yolk Cholesterol as Obtained from Probiotic pr Prebiotic Layer Diet Supplementation. *Feedinfo News Service*, [Available Online]. [Accessed 2010 October 11]. Internet site: <[http:// www.feedinfo.com](http://www.feedinfo.com) >.
- Chen, Y. C. and Chen, T. C. (2004): Mineral utilization in layers as influenced by dietary oligofructose and inulin. *Int. J. Poult. Sci.*, 3, 442–445.
- Chowdhury, R.; Islam, K. M.; Khan, M. J.; Karim, M. R.; Haque, M. N.; Khatun, M. and Pesti, G. M. (2009): Effect of citric acid, avilamycin and their combination on the performance, tibia ash and immune status of broilers. *Poult. Sci.*, 88: 1616-1622.
- Coakes, S. J.; Steed, L. G. and Ong, C. (2009) *SPSS : analysis without anguish : version 16 for Windows / Sheridan J. Coakes, Lyndall Steed, Clara Ong* John Wiley & Sons Australia, Milton, Qld.
- Cruickshank, G. (2002): Gut microflora – the key to healthy broiler growing. *Poultry World*, July, 14.
- Denbow, D. M. (2000): Gastrointestinal anatomy and physiology. Pages 299–625 in *Sturkie's Avian Physiology*. 5th ed. G. Causey Whittow, ed. Acad. Press, San Diego, CA.
- Dhawale, A. (2005): Better egg shell quality with a gut acidifier. *Poult. Int.* 44: 18-21.
- Duncan, D. B. (1955): Multiple range and multiple F test. *Biometrics* 11: 1-42.
- Eslick, M. L. and McDaniel, G. R. (1992): Interrelationships between fertility and hatchability of eggs from broiler breeder hens. *J. App. Poult. Res.* 1:156–159.
- Finucane, M.; Spring, P. and Newman, K. E. (1999): Incidence of mannose sensitive adhesions in enteric bacteria. *Poult. Sci.* 78 (Suppl. 1):139. (Abstr.).
- Gama, N. M. S. Q.; Olivera, M. B. C.; Santin, E. and Berchieri, J. (2000): Supplementation with organic acids in diets of laying hens. *Ciencia Rur.*, Santa Maria, 30: 499-502.
- Gar, M.; Fonseca, J. B.; Soares, R. T. R. N.; Silva, M. A. and Souza, C. L. M. (2001.): Performance of commercial brown egg layers fed dried yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) of sugar-cane. *Revista Brasileira de Ciencia Avicola*, 3, 163–171.
- Grunewald, K. K. (1982): Serum cholesterol level in rats fed skim milk fermented by *lactobacillus acidophilus*. *J. F. Sci.* 47: 2075-2097.

- Guclu, B. K. (2003): The effect of mannanoligosaccharide on fattening performance of quails. *Indian Vet. J.* 80 (10), 1018-1021.
- Guclu, B. K. (2011). Effects of probiotic and prebiotic (mannanoligosaccharide) supplementation on performance, egg quality and hatchability in quail breeders. *Ankara Üniv. Vet. Fak. Derg.* 58: 27- 32.
- Guerrero, M. R. (1995): Using yeast culture and lactic acid bacteria in broiler breeder diets. Pages 371–378 in *Biotechnology in the Feed Industry*. T. P. Lyons and K. A. Jacques, ed. Nottingham Univ. Press, Nottingham.
- Hassan, S. M.; Mady, M. E.; Cartwright, A. L.; Sabri, H. M. and Mobarak, M. S. (2003): Effect of early feed restriction on reproductive performance in Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*). *Poult. Sci.* 82:1163-1169.
- Kirchgesner, M. and Roth, F.X. (1988): Ergotropic effects of organic acids in the rearing of piglets and the fattening of pigs. *Übersichten zur tiererenährung*, 16: 93-108.
- Lenzi, A., L. Gandini, M. Picardo, F. Tramer, G. Sandri, and E. Panfili. (2000): Lipid peroxidation damage of spermatozoa polyunsaturated fatty acids: scavenger mechanisms and possible scavenger therapies. *Front. Biosci.* 5:11–15.
- Liem, A.; Pesti, G. M. and H. M. Edwards Jr. (2008): The Effect of Several Organic Acids on Phytate Phosphorus Hydrolysis in Broiler Chicks. *Poult. Sci.* 87:689–693.
- Liu, Z.; Qi, G. and Yoon, I. (2002): Effect of yeast culture on production parameters and intestinal micro flora in laying hens. Page 89 in *Poult. Sci. Assn. 91st Annual Meeting Abstracts*. August 11–14, 2002. Newark, DE. Abstract No: 381.
- Luiten, E. (2003): Size does matters: yolk utilization and chick length as parameter for embryo development. *Hybro technical info*. <http://www.chicklength.com>.
- Lutz, T. and Scharrer, E. (1991): Effect of short-chain fatty acids on calcium absorption by the rat colon. *Experimental Physiology*, 76, 615–618.
- McDaniel, G. R. (1991): The importance of biological products in poultry operations, small improvements, major benefits. Pages 293–300 in *Biotechnology in the Feed Industry*. Alltech's Technical Publications, Nicholasville, KY.
- McDaniel, G. R. and Sefton, T. (1991): Effect of yeast culture (*Yeasacc1026*) supplementation on broiler breeders. *Poult. Sci.* 70(Suppl. 1):172. (Abstr.).
- McNamara, D. J. (2000): Eggs, dietary cholesterol and heart disease risk: An international perspective. Pages 55–63 in *Egg Nutrition and Biotech*. J. S. Sim, ed. CABI Publishing, New York, NY.
- Miazzo, R. Peralta, M. F.; Magnoli, C. Salvano, M.; Ferrero, S.; Chiacchiera, S. M.; Carvalho, E. C. Q.; Rosa, C. A. R. and Dalcero, A. (2005): Efficacy of sodium bentonite as a detoxifier of broiler feed contaminated with aflatoxin and fumonisin. *Poult. Sci.*, 84: 1-8.
- Mohan, B., Kadirvel, R.; Bhaskaran, M. and Natarajan, A. (1995): Effect of probiotic supplementation on serum/yolk cholesterol and on eggshell thickness in layers. *Br. Poult. Sci.* 36:799–803.
- Mroz, Z.; Jongbloed, A. W.; Partanen, K. H.; Verman, K.; Kemme, P. A. and Kogut, J. (2000): The effects of calcium benzoate in diets with or without organic acids on dietary buffering capacity, apparent digestibility, retention of nutrients and manure characteristics in swine. *J. Anim. Sci.*, 78: 2622-2632.
- NRC National Research Council (1994): *Nutritional requirements of poultry*". 9th Rev. Ed. National academy press, Washington, DC.

- Olawumi, S. O. and Ogunlade, J. T. (2008): Phenotypic correlations between some external and internal egg quality traits in the exotic isa brown layer breeders. *Asian J. Poult. Sci.* 2(1): 30-35.
- Omogbenigun, F. O.; Nyachoti, C. M. and Slominski, B. A. (2003): The effect of supplementing microbial phytase and organic acids to a corn-soybean based diet fed to early weaned pigs. *J. Anim. Sci.*, 81, 1806–1813.
- Onifade, A.; Odunsi, A.; Babatunde, G.; Olorede, B. and Muma, E. (1999): Comparison of the supplemental effects of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and antibiotics in low-protein and high-fibre diet fed to broiler chickens. *Arch. Tierernaehr.* 52 (1): 29-39.
- Önol, A. G.; Yağın, S. (1995): The usage of baker's yeast in laying hen rations. *Vet. J. Ankara Univ.* 42, 161–167 (in Turkish with English summary).
- Panda, A. K., Reddy, M. R.; Rama Rao, S.V. and Praharaaj, N. K. (2003): Production performance, serum/yolk cholesterol and immune competence of white leghorn layers as influenced by dietary supplementation with probiotic. *Trop. Anim. Health Prod.* 35, 85-94.
- Park, J. H.; Park, G. G. and Ryu, K. S. (2002): Effect of feeding organic acid mixture and yeast culture on performance and egg quality of laying hens. *Korean J. Poult. Sci.*, 29, 109–115.
- Park, S. W.; Burnham, M. R.; Branton, S. L.; Gerard, P. D.; Womack, S. K. and Peebles, E. D. (2009): Influence of supplemental dietary poultry fat on the performance of commercial layers inoculated before or at the onset of lay with F-strain *Mycoplasma gallisepticum*. *Poult. Sci.* 88:1365–1372.
- Pasin, G.; Smith, G. M. and O'Mahony, M. (1998): Rapid determination of total cholesterol in egg yolk using commercial diagnostic cholesterol reagent. *Food Chem.*, Vol. 61, No. 1/2, pp. 255-259.
- Petek, M.; Baspınar, H.; Ogan, M. and Balci, F. (2005): Effects of egg weight and length of storage period on hatchability and subsequent laying performance of quail. *Turk. J. Vet. Anim. Sci.*, 2:537-542.
- Pop, I. M. (2002): *Aditivi furajeri*. Editura Pim, Iasi, Romania.
- Radcliffe, J. S.; Zhang, Z. and Kornegay, E. T. (1998): The effects of microbial phytase, citric acid, and their interaction in a corn-soybean meal-based diet for weanling pigs. *J. Anim. Sci.*, 76, 1880–1886.
- Radu-Rusu, C. G. and Pop, I. M. (2009): Improvement of laying hen performances by dietary mannaoligosaccharides supplementation. *Universitatea de Științe Agricole și Medicină Veterinară Iași Lucrări Științifice - vol. 52, Seria Zootehnie*, pp 215-219.
- Ramunė, Č.; Diana, G.; Vytaitas, S.; Rasa, B.; Inga, K.; Danius, V. and Vytaitas, S. (2010): Effect of the yeast culture feed additive on productivity and egg quality of laying quails. *Vet. Ir Zootech. (Vet Med Zoot)*. T. 52 (74).
- Robinson, F. E.; Renema, R. A.; Bouvier, L.; Feddes, J. J. R.; Zuidhof, M. J.; Wilson, J. L.; Newcombe, M. and McKay, R. I. (1998): Effects of photostimulatory lighting and feed allocation in female broiler breeders. 2. Egg and chick production characteristics. *Canadian J. Anim. Sci.* 78, 615-623.
- Rojas Ramirez, E.; Avila-Gonzalez, E. and Casarin-Valverde, A. (1985): Nutritional value of yeast as a source of protein in diets for laying hens and the determination of true metabolizable energy value. *Poult. Abst.* 11, 659.
- Roque, L. and Soares, M. C. (1994): Effects of eggshell quality and broiler breeder age on hatchability. *Poult. Sci.* 73:1838-1845.

- Sakurai, H. (1983): Influence of ambient temperature and light length for rearing term on growth and egg production characteristics of Japanese quail. *Japan. Poult. Sci.*, 20, 1–7.
- Sefton, T. (1991): El concepto de los probióticos y la producción avícola, evaluación de datos de rendimiento. X Ciclo de Conferencias Internacionales de Avicultura. AMENA 378.
- Sengor, E.; Yardimci, M.; Cetingul, S.; Bayram, I.; Sahin, H. and Dogan, I. (2007): Effects of short chain fatty acid (SCFA) supplementation on performance and egg characteristics of old breeder hens. *South African J. Anim. Sci.*, 37, 158–163.
- Shanawany, M. M. (1994): Quail production system, A review. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome.
- Shao L. P.; Zhou, L. J.; Li, G. P.; Lin, F. P.; Fei, Z. F.; Jin, T.; Lin, Y. Q.; Chen, Z. B.; and Chen, X. D. (2000): Effects of oral administration of mannan-oligosaccharide on immune responses and blood GSH-Px, SOD activities in suckling piglets. *Chin. J. Vet. Sci.* 20:257–260.
- Shashidhara, R. G. and Devegowda, G. (2003): Effect of dietary mannan oligosaccharide on broiler breeder Production traits and immunity. *Poult. Sci.*, 82:1319–1325.
- Shyam Sunder, G.; Pandey, N. K. and Sadagopan, V. R. (1990): Effect of dietary calcium and phosphorus levels on production parameters and egg quality traits of White Leghorn layers fed inactive dry yeast. *Indian J. Anim. Sci.*, 60, 350–354.
- Snedecor, G. W. and Cochran, W. C. (1989): *Statistical methods* 8th Ed. Iowa State Univ. Press/Ames, Iowa-50010.
- Soltan, M. A. (2008): Effect of organic acid supplementation on egg production, egg quality, and some blood serum parameters in laying hens. *Int. J. of Poult. Sci.*, 7, 613–621.
- Spring, P.; Wenk, C.; Dawson, K. A.; Newman, K. E. (2000): The effects of dietary mannanoligosaccharide on cecal parameters and the concentrations of enteric bacteria in the ceca *Salmonella*-challenged broiler chicks. *Poult Sci*, 79, 205-211.
- Stanley, V. G.; Brown, C. and Sefton, T. (2000): Single and combined effects of dietary protease and mannanoligosaccharide on the performance of laying hens. *Poult. Sci.* 79(Suppl. 1):62. (Abstr.).
- Stanley, V. G.; Gray, C.; Daley, M.; Krueger, W. F. and Sefton, A. E. (2004): An alternative to antibiotic-based drugs in feed for enhancing performance of broilers grown on *Eimeria spp.* - infected litter. *Poult. Sci.* 83:39–44.
- Surai, P. F.; Fujihara, N.; Speake, B. K.; Brillard, J-P.; Wishart, G. J. and Sparks, N. H. C. (2001): Polyunsaturated fatty acids, lipid peroxidation and antioxidant protection in avian semen. *Asi.-Aust. J. Anim. Sci.* 14:1024–1050.
- Swiątkiewicz, S.; Koreleski, J. and Arczewska, A. (2010): Laying performance and eggshell quality in laying hens fed diets supplemented with prebiotics and organic acids. *Czech J. Anim. Sci.*, 55, 294–306.
- Tarasewicz, Z. (1998): Biologiczna ocena oligosacharydów wyizolowanych z nasion łubinu wąskolistnego (*Lupinus angustifolius*) zastosowanych w żywieniu przepiórek reprodukcyjnych (Biological assesment of oligosaccharides isolated from emir variety lupin (*Lupinus angustifolius*) seeds in feeding of reproductive quail stock). In Polish, summary in English. Rozprawy, nr 186, Agricultural University of Szczecin.

- Tarasewicz, Z.; Dańczak, A.; Szczerbińska, D.; Majewska, D. and Romaniszyn, K. (1998): Użytkowość brojlerów przepiórczych żywionych dietami z udziałem BIOMOS- u i oligosacharydów wyizolowanych z nasion łubinu. Zesz. Nauk. Przeg. Hod., Chów i Hodowla Drobiu, 36, 245–255.
- Tarasewicz, Z.; Szczerbinska, D.; Ligocki, M.; Danczak, A.; Majewska D. and Kurzawa, J. (2004): Effect of the origin of quails on their utility type and selected egg quality traits. Elec. J. Polish Agri. Universities, Animal Husbandry 7 (2), 1-7
- Tyler, C. (1961): Shell strength. Its measurement and its relationship to other factors. Br. Poult. Sci., 2: 3-19.
- Ursini, F.; Heim, S.; Kliess, M.; Maiorino, M.; Roveri, A.; Wissing, J. and Flohe, L. (1999): Dual function of the selenoprotein PHGPx during sperm maturation. Science 285:1393–1396.
- Waldroup, A. L.; Skinner, J. T.; Hierholzer, R. E. and Waldroup, P. W. (1993): an evaluation of fructooligosaccharide in diets for broiler chickens and effects on salmonella contamination of carcasses. Poult. Sci. 72: 643-650.
- Woodard, A. E.; Abplanalp, H.; Wilson, W. O. and Vohra, P. (1973): Japanese quail husbandry in the laboratory (*Coturnix coturnix Japonica*). Department of Avian Sci., Univ. of California Davis, CA 95616.
- Yalcin, S.; Ergun, A.; Coplan, I. and Sehu, A. (1990): Yumurta tavugu rasyonlarinda findik ici kabunun kullanilma olanaklarinin arastirilmesi. Vet. J. Ankara Univ., 3: 485-498.
- Yalcin, S.; Ozsoy, B.; Erol, H. and Yalcin, S. (2008): Yeast culture supplementation to laying hen diets containing soybean meal or sunflower seed meal and its effect on performance, egg quality traits, and blood chemistry. J. Appl. Poult. Res., 17:229-236.
- Yalcin, S.; Oğuz, F.; Güçlü, B. and Yalcin, S. (2009): Effects of dietary dried baker's yeast on the performance, egg traits and blood parameters in laying quails. Trop. Anim. Health Prod. Vol. 41, No. 1, 5-10.
- Yesilbag, D. and Colpan, I. (2006): Effects of organic acid supplemented diets on growth performance, egg production and quality and on serum parameters in laying hens. Rev. Med. Vét., 157, 280–284.
- Yildiz G.; Sacakli, P. and Gungor, T. (2006): The effect of dietary Jerusalem artichoke (*Helianthus tuberosus*) on performance, egg quality characteristics and egg cholesterol content in laying hens. Czech J. Anim. Sci., 8, 349–354.
- Yuan, T.; Lein, R. J. and Mcdaniel, G. R. (1994): Effect of increased rearing period body weights and early photostimulation on broiler breeder egg production. World's Poult. Sci. 73. :792–800.
- Zeidler, G. (2000): Egg products around the world: Today and tomorrow. Pages 65–92 in Egg Nutrition and Biotechnology. J. S. Sim, ed. CABI Publishing, New York, NY.
- Zeinab, M. A. Abdo; Madein, A. H.; Soliman, A. Z. M. and Awed-Allah, M. A. (2001): Effects of inclusion of some probiotic preparations on the laying performance. J. Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ. 26 (10): 5985-5996.
- Zhang, A. W.; Lee, B. D.; Lee, S. K.; Lee, K. W.; An, G.H.; Song, K. B. and Lee, C. H. (2005): Effects of yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) cell components on growth performance, meat quality, and ileal mucosa development of broiler chicks. J. Poult. Sci. 84:1015–1021.
- Zhou, L. J.; Shao, L. P.; Li, G. P. and Lin, F. P. (1999): Effect of mannan oligosaccharide and *Streptococcus [Enterococcus] faecalis* on the activities of superoxide desmutase (SOD) and glutathione peroxidase (GSH-px) in the blood of chickens and piglets. J. Fujian. Agric. Univ. 28:200–203.